

THE EDUCATIONAL HERITAGE OF THE GREAT ORIENTAL THINKERS AND ITS SPIRITUAL SUPPORT IN THE FAMILY SOCIETY

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Abstract. *The spirituality, history, unique customs and traditions of any nation or nation cannot be imagined without national values. The family environment prepares the ground for the child to grow up to be moral, polite, honest, hardworking, honest and sincere.*

Keywords: *Alisher Navoi, education, science and manners are embodied in such sayings, children, the melody on the curtains.*

Introduction

As we all know, our holy books and values, the legacy of great Eastern thinkers always call us to live with honest work, courage, generosity and humility, justice and kindness. Of course, the spirituality, history, unique customs and traditions of any nation or nation cannot be imagined without national values.

The wisdom of Eastern scholars, including Ibn Sina, Nizamulk's "Politics", "Saodatnama" by Nasir Khisrav, "Roshnoyinoma", "Kutadgu Bilig" by Yusuf Khos Hajib, Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu Lugatit Turk", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibat ul-haqaiq", The wisdom of Abu Rayhan Beruni, "Nightmare" by Kaikovus, "Mahbub ul-Qulub" by Alisher Navoi, Attention to child education is reflected in Hossein Vaiz Koshifi's works such as "Akhlai muqsini". From the mentioned works, it is possible to come to a general conclusion that if the child is the happiness of the parents, education is the child's today, tomorrow and future. That is why education is a social phenomenon. Education has existed since the beginning of human society. After all, in order for a person to be the most perfect breed on earth, he must first be educated. There is a saying among our people that "an educator must first of all be educated". Ibn Sina said to the educators, "Whatever advice you give to someone, that is, first of all, do it yourself."

Research materials and methodology. It is the duty of all of us to use the opinions, advices and wisdom of thinkers in raising children, expanding and enriching their spiritual worldview, and raising a mature person. Articles 76-80 of Chapter XIV Family, Children and Youth of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, effective from May 1, 2023 - Family is the main link of society and it is under the protection of society and the state, about marriage, that the state creates social, economic, legal and other conditions for the full development of the family, that parents and their substitutes support their children until they reach adulthood, that they are obliged to take care of their upbringing, education, healthy, mature and all-round development, motherhood, fatherhood and childhood are protected by the state, and adult children capable of working are their parents The fact that the family is important in the politics of Daval has been legally confirmed in terms of the fact that they are obliged to take care of their mothers. The family, which is the cradle of education, is a sacred space that preserves the continuity of every people, nation, ensures the development of national values, gives birth to and educates mentally and

physically perfect generation, and raises patriotic defenders of the country. A person receives the first education from the family, love, mother's milk and special alla. Its influence is deeply rooted in human nature and soul. A child's perfection, mentality, kindness, and manners are formed on the basis of the internal, specific rules established in each family.

In particular, as President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "It is clear to all of us that the noblest dreams and goals of every family, life interests, first of all, are manifested and realized in the form of their children." The issue of children's spiritual education is also important. Scientist Safo Okhr, who explained the word spirituality, said: "Spirituality" means the beauty, generosity, nobility, loyalty to one's promise, imagination, learning, wisdom, tolerance, neatness and purity of human behavior. the innocence of the heart, politeness and such pleasant customs are understood", - puts forward the opinion. In his book "Bizkim, Uzbeklar", Abdukahhor Ibrohimov says: "A person can be enlightened without using the word enlightenment a lot, be enlightened, and be spiritual without using the phrase spirituality abusively. Because these are not in the language - enlightenment - in the mind, spirituality - in the heart." According to the scientist, today's women, along with their activities in the development of the society, instill enlightenment in their minds and spirituality in their hearts, they are a kind mother for children in the family, a beloved wife for their husband, and moreover, they are warm and moderate in the family. it is also important to remember that they are creative and sweet mistresses who can create climate and conditions. "The type of education and the method of instilling it in children are different and mutually necessary. However, the education of kindness, honesty, and truthfulness is the most urgent topic of our day."

Search results. In fact, a well-rounded person is a bright prospect for the future of every people and nation! Human qualities that accompany a person for a lifetime - kindness, goodness, creativity, dedication, loyalty, courage, honesty, and compassion are first formed in the family environment. The family environment prepares the ground for the child to grow up to be moral, polite, honest, hardworking, honest and sincere. Family upbringing plays an important role in the development of a child in the future. For a child, a healthy socio-spiritual environment in the family is a source of spiritual and moral values, traditions, social experience and skills. It develops in the process of education. The essence of education is to train a person for life. Family education has a deep impact on children's mental world, emotions and feelings. The lifestyle of family members often determines the mental mood, imagination and emotions of their children. At the same time, Abdulla Awlani said that "to educate a child for his health and happiness is to keep his body clean, correct his profession from a young age, teach him good manners, and protect him from bad manners", Abdurauf Fitrat's "not only the family is responsible for raising children, but all members of society are responsible for bringing them to adulthood", As stated in the Hadith Sharif, "no parent can gift their child more than good upbringing and manners", as the folk wisdom says, "a child is like a piece of white paper, filling it with good writings is the duty of parents and teachers", philosopher George Santayana's "family is one of the masterpieces of nature", Abu Ali ibn Sina's "It is necessary to understand how many ideas about science and manners are embodied in such sayings, which express the content of etiquette culture and the place of the family in the education and upbringing of a child." It is necessary to raise children in the family in such a way that their desire for happiness never fades, does not fade, but grows blue," said Fitrat. Yes, of course, education plays an important role in human life. Since the child spends most of his time with his mother, some people have formed the attitude of looking at upbringing as the duty of mothers. What about father? How important is the role of fathers in raising children, especially

boys? Or is mother's education enough to make a person a perfect person? Was it possible for the father to support the family financially and financially? No, of course. According to experts, as the outlook of women and men are fundamentally different, fathers should be more involved in the education of boys. Because the father's role is very important in the upbringing of a boy and a child in general. A man is the fortress of the house, the bulwark of the family in all good and bad times. If there is a problem in the family, the family members rely on him. Therefore, the role of the father in the upbringing of a boy is incomparable, and he has a number of responsibilities. Children brought up in families where the father is the head develop a positive sense of admiration and respect for the father. This is what keeps him from going beyond the "drawn line", from violating various social norms accepted in our life and, in turn, from being subjected to various social sanctions.

In life, mother is often a teacher and coach for a girl child, and a father is a teacher for a boy. Raising a boy in a family is a complex and long-lasting special process, which should begin long before the birth of a child. That is, the future parents' health, lineage, outlook, inner and outer world, morals, moral and physical readiness for marriage are important in the upbringing of the future child. Each family member, neighbor, neighborhood, educational institution, community is equally responsible for raising a boy in the family. It is not wrong to say that the role of the father is the most important in this system. Also, one of the famous word artists, Oybek is a great writer who has made a worthy contribution to children's literature.

Discussions. He enriched the treasury of Uzbek literature with his novels and short stories, scientific-theoretical, political, art-journalistic works, translations, wonderful poems, epics, and stories, and wrote the story "Alisher's Youth" (1967), which tells about the childhood years of the great Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi. Ulugh Navoi was one of Oibek's favorite figures. The writer tells about this in one of his articles: "Navoi's poetry and Navoi's image always attracted my heart like a strong sun". I had a great inclination and desire to create the image of Navoi in my works. Since I was young, I loved reading Navoi's immortal, literary poems, his charming ghazals became more and more engrossing in my heart, their form and content intoxicated and enchanted my heart... He was in my heart, in my mind, he occupied my whole existence. Whenever I walked, I always thought of Navoi. I could feel and see his meaningful, intelligent eyes, his always kind, compassionate, noble face, his pure and great heart." The story tells about Alisher's childhood years (from the age of four), the development of Alisher's character is described in a continuous connection with the events and conflicts of the external environment at that time. It is truthfully described that the family's sincerity and polite behavior of Beka Ghiyosiddin and Gulbegim, who had a very high position among the ruling circle, were important in the development of their child Alisher, both physically and mentally. In introducing students to the heroes of the story and describing the improvement of Alisher's qualities, Aybek describes how he can be a role model for the younger generation in terms of family environment as follows: Masterfully using the image of hospitality in Ghiyosiddin Kikhiny's house, guests, relatives, and close friends gather in the bright spacious hotel, and it begins with an image of great happiness and sincere conversation, portrays him as someone who commands everyone's respect. Stating that many people call Alisher his father Ghiyosiddin Kikhiny, and his close friends often call him Kikhy Bahadir, Alisher's mother Gulbegim Beka is among the guests who came to Malika Gavharshad's palace, "Handsome Gulbegim, with a handsome figure, white face, thin eyebrows and dark eyes with a twinkle of love, were the best factors of beauty. "This twenty-five-year-old girl, dressed with great taste and taste,

immediately caught the eye at gatherings, her face was warm and pleasant," he describes. Thus, at the very beginning of the work, Aybek draws the attention of the readers to introduce the wonderful and pleasant qualities of Alisher's parents. Aybek impressively describes the social and political environment of that time and the scene of terrible battles for the throne, and the fact that he is the uncle of Kabuli Alisher, who is famous for his Turkish poems, on the basis of a tape of mutual conversation:

"Ulugbek is a distinguished scientist who discovered eternity in the world of science. This breed, whose hearts are the embodiment of all sciences, will forever be a bright star in the book of our history. In the course of hospitality, young Alisher learns about Sultan Ulugbek's incomparable knowledge and wisdom, and that he is an entrepreneur representative of the kingdom. Alisher looks at these qualities with deep love. Alisher skillfully described how his parents, the time he studied with Hossein Boygaro, his uncle, and others, especially the stories about Ulugbek's discoveries, were a creative school in the formation and improvement of Alisher's mind. Aybek truthfully describes young Alisher's sincere respect for adults, his ability to understand poetry with deep taste, and his understanding. The unique qualities of young Alisher's character were manifested in his childhood. Alisher's cleverness, sincere respect for elders, delicate feeling of poetry, expressive reading of ghazals, especially his thinking that "thinking is better than galloping horses" leave a great impression on the reader. Of course, these qualities alone did not serve as a sufficient basis for Alisher to become a great statesman and a great poet. Aybek Alisher was able to artistically justify the formation process of Alisher's character through each scene, line, dialogue, supporting character and character's relationship.

Alisher's passion for study and school is described in his language: "Hunting is fun, but school is the best necessity. School teaches many secrets of life," describing his interest in science. At the same time, it is noted that the conversation of his parents, relatives and others, poets' ghazals had a great influence on Alisher.

Another characteristic of Alisher is that he listens carefully to the opinions of adults and tries to find out who is right and who is wrong. In the same way, the character of young Alisher is gradually formed. In the story, Alisher's attitude to art is convincingly reflected in his own scenes. In particular, the images expressed on the basis of the flute piece are also instructive for today's young readers. Especially grandfather's saying "There are many secrets of pleasure... I have tried a lot, and when I grow up, I will become a knower and a wise man. Halitdan's tongue pierces a coin, I see the fire of his chest in his eyes. He listens to ghazals with pleasure, he has a great passion for musical instruments" are instructive in this respect. The impact of the hanging of seven prisoners brought from the village on the expression of attitude to the era in Alisher's character is great. Aybek describes Alisher's desire for science and literature by describing how he tries to understand the meaning of the Qur'an, learns Persian-Arabic languages, skillfully reads verses and ghazals in Turkish (mother tongue) and memorizes many ghazals, tries to read proverbs, parables, and fairy tales with love. Alisher now understands more deeply the terrible battles between the princes, the bloody wars, the turbulent events of his time, the enmity between the father and the son, and his circle of thought expands day by day. Aybek has a keen sense of the Turkish and Persian language, its national spirit, wealth, and the meaning of words and phrases that lived five hundred years ago. Let's remember the image of the old piper. He is actually from a poor class of poor; his profession is to make and play the flute. Baba cannot imagine the true meaning of life without a flute. The young reader learns from the words and conversations of this old man that his

profession is playing the flute. The old man's age is immediately felt in the meaningful, meaningful and clear phrases in his speech. "... The flute is an ancient instrument of ours, it sings the sorrows and sorrows of sad and sad souls, its beautiful sound fills the hearts with joy at weddings, it is a wonderful magical instrument.

Alisherbek fell in love - let's find out. If my son wants, maybe he will be a famous musician... The melody in the heart sits on the flute with the breath... The fingers put the melody on the curtains." Aybek once again demonstrated that he is the owner of artistic skills by promoting the ideas of humanity, goodness, humanity, generosity, love for young people through the images of such old luminaries. Alisher's upbringing as a real person was greatly influenced by the spiritual influence of Ghiyosiddin Kikhiny, Mistress Gulbegim, grandfather the servant, and uncle Mirsaid. In the story, Aybek was able to convincingly describe Alisher's great love and respect for the deserts of Turkestan, the great mountains, the customs of the peoples who lived here, and their "beautiful, sweet and colorful" language. Aibek's skill in creating personal effects was also clearly seen in this work. He often reveals the positive or negative spiritual world of the heroes by drawing a clear image and appearance. The writer's skill in artistic language and image creation ensured the folk spirit of the story, and Aybek was able to create true impressions of the life of our people in the distant past through the story "Alisher's Youth".

Conclusion. In conclusion, while raising a child in the family and in educational institutions imposes a great sense of responsibility on each of us, first of all, we must remember that the child is the continuation of our life, how hard the thorn in his leg is in the heart of the parents, for the sake of the child. We, the team of parents and pedagogues, should always keep in mind that his behavior and manners should be treated as a first-class issue. From this point of view, in child education, pedagogues should be in close cooperation with family and community, they should hold regular creative meetings and educational activities based on a strict schedule on spiritual topics, and based on their initiative and suggestions, they should be disciplined and It is necessary to pay attention to the development and practical implementation of the measures.

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